

**SOCIAL MEDIA EXPOSURE: ITS EFFECT ON THE PERFORMANCE IN
MATHEMATICS OF GENERAL ACADEMIC STRAND STUDENTS
IN A UNIVERSITY IN SULU, SOUTHERN PHILIPPINES**

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ABSTRACT

This descriptive-survey study was conducted to investigate the relationship between social media exposure and the performance of the students in mathematics. This study will merit school administrators and teachers to be fully cognizant of the true nature of social media and its effect on the learning of the students. This will help them create countermeasures and actions that will address the academic problems of the students. This will also be beneficial to the parents who are directly concerned with the education of students considering school performance in different disciplines. The students will also be aware of the effects of the social media and be able to minimize and strategize the time consumption on social media. A researcher-made questionnaire was constructed and distributed to eighty (80) grade 11 students that were selected randomly from GAS 1 and GAS 4 at Mindanao State University – Sulu Senior High School Department. A 50-50 % proportion between the number of male and female were observed in the selection of the respondents. t-test was used to analyze the data, interpret the results, and arrive at the implications of the study. After a series of analyzation of data, the researchers present the following findings; Social media exposure did not significantly affect the performance of students in mathematics, The performance in mathematics of light users, average users, and heavy users of social media did not significantly differ from one another, There is no significant difference between the number of hours spent by male and female students, The performance in mathematics of male and female students did not significantly differ, even though female students use social media longer than male students.

Keywords: *social media exposure, academic performance, mathematics*

INTRODUCTION

Twenty first Century marks the beginning of technological boom with the increase and widespread use of internet and social media. The use of social media has skyrocketed in the past ten years with the change of human lifestyle and norms. Social media has become the new trend among people and is widely appreciated around all ages as it offers a variety of benefits and opportunities, one of these, is its contribution to traverse the challenge of learning as uttered by Sabbaha, N. et. al, (2024) Indeed, learning is the soul of education that eliminates ignorance within individual's mind, it is an ability possessed by human being that plays a crucial role in the existence of human life, from the moment a person was brought into this world, the process of learning begins until he or she reaches the stage of late adulthood which means that learning is a continuous process. Jailani, A. et.al, (2024) stated that although the pandemic may have passed by now, its effects are still felt, thus education needs to continue. Indeed, education is the key to success, thus it shouldn't be interrupted, so the government has come up with a way to meet the demands of the learners while allowing the children to continue their education, and this should be credited to technology or its features such as social media platforms.

Balla, F.J. (2024) In today's 21st century, students are facing multiple problems such as explanations based on science and technology and it will likely offer corrective measures of difficulties and definitely one way to traverse these difficulties and challenges is to have Technology-Mediated Instruction, it is an approach to education that combines online educational materials and opportunities for interaction online with physical place-based classroom methods. Mading, F. (2024).

Social media creates a platform where a person can create content and interact with any person from around the world. It also allows a person to fully use freedom of expression by openly sharing thoughts and opinions about all the things that are happening around the world. Social media will continue developing as the time goes by, and it will continue to introduce many different things. Indeed, social media has become a part of human's daily lives, and it is completely unimaginable to live without it nowadays.

But social media is not just about the benefits and advancements, because like any other things it also has its own drawbacks. There is a popular accepted saying that everything excessive is harmful, the same goes to social media. With the large amount of time everyone spends on social media, it is not surprising for many bad incidents to happen involving it. Things like cyberbullying and scams became mundane and pervasive around the world and are most of the times not given the proper action it deserves. It is because perpetrators can easily hide through social media itself. Lesser emotional connections between families, peers and relatives became normal as every person is glued to gadgets scrolling through different social media sites. These are just some of the downsides of social media, and there are some more of it that needs cognizance and attention.

The ones that are greatly affected by all these stuffs are the teenagers because they are the heaviest users of social media. It is rare nowadays to find a teenager that does not use social media, if so, mostly are teenagers from rural areas or from some places that have

a weak internet reception. The amount of time teens spend on social media is pretty disturbing. On the Philippines alone, 31.8% of Facebook users were between the ages of 18 and 24. According to Common Sense Media, teens spend an average of nine hours a day online (paywall). In 2015, The Pew Research Center reported that 92% of teens go online daily which indicates that their day to day lives are woven by social media. That number might have increased exponentially as we enter 2021, all the more so that social media today is far more upgraded than it was 5 years ago. This only serves as a wake-up call, especially to the parents to be fully aware of the treats of social media as it might also be a hindrance to the academic performance of the teens.

One of the alarming effects of social media is how it influences the performance and attitude of students towards mathematics. Mathematics is one of the core courses in any curricular programs and as such school administrators and teachers should know the various factors that affect the academic performance of the students in Mathematics. With the advent of social media, the opportunities of understanding and learning mathematics became prevalent. According to Fisher (2011), the use of social media has big influence on teachers and learners compared to traditional educational system due to the opportunities provided to connect and collaborate in a much easier manner. On the other hand, some studies suggest that social media affects the student's academic performance negatively. In a study released by the researchers at The Miriam Hospitals Center for Behavioral and Preventive Medicine, there was a great link between social media use and poor academic performance. However, other studies like Ahmed and Qazi (2011) conducted on the same topic revealed no correlation between social media and students' academic performance.

As aforementioned, there are many contradicting studies that suggest that social media can affect the performance of students positively and negatively. This reason piques the interest of the researchers to study on the relationship of today's more advance social media on the performance of students in mathematics. Specifically, this study wants to find out if there is a great link between social media exposure and the performance of students in mathematics. Today, it is crucial to determine the effect of social media on the academic performance of students. Technology is rapidly booming from year to year and the younger generations are the ones caught up in this rapid change.

Research Questions

This study attempted to determine the relationship between social media exposure and the performance in mathematics of grade 11 GAS 1 and GAS 4 students at Mindanao State University-Sulu. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. Is there a significant difference in the performance of the students in mathematics using social media?
2. Is there a significant difference in the performance of students in mathematics according to the number of hours of using social media?
3. Is there a significant difference between the number of hours spent by male and female students?

4. Is there a significant difference in the performance of the students in mathematics using social media when grouped according to gender?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

The setting of the study was conducted at Mindanao State University-Sulu. The Mindanao State University-Sulu is the only university in Jolo, Sulu located at Capitol Site near the Provincial Capitol. The said university is composed of seven (7) colleges excluding the Mindanao State University-Sulu Laboratory High School.

Sampling Method

This study used Simple Random Sampling in the selection of respondents. In selecting the sections to be studied, the researchers put the names of grade 11 GAS sections in a box and picked two sections randomly. By pure chance, the researchers selected the GAS 1 and GAS 2 sections. The researchers did the same process in the selection of the students from the two sections. All the names of the students from GAS 1 and GAS 2 were put in two separated box grouped according to their gender. The researchers selected forty male students and 40 female students randomly for a total of eighty respondents. The researchers believed that selecting eighty students as the respondents was enough to gather the necessary information. The researchers then coordinated the advisers GAS 1 and GAS 2 to ask for the first quarter final grades of the selected students in General Mathematics.

Research Instrument

The main tool used in this study is a researcher-made questionnaire-checklist and the grades of the students in the first quarter. Set of questionnaire-checklist was constructed for the students to answer. The questionnaire-checklist consisted of the amount of time the students spend on social media per day just as follows;

1. I spend less than an hour a day using social media
2. I spend 2 to 3 hours a day using social media
3. I spend 4 to 8 hours a day using social media

This questionnaire-checklist determined if the students are light user, medium users or heavy users of social media. Students that spend not over an hour a day are light users. Students that spend 2 to 3 hours a day are average users and students that spend 4 to 8 hours are considered heavy users.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Throughout the study, the researcher used t-test for independent samples and to analyze the data, interpret the result and to arrive at the implication of the study.

Scope and Delimitation

This study focuses on the social media exposure: its effect on the performance of student in mathematics. the participant of this study is delimited to selected forty male students and 40 female students randomly coming from Mindanao State University – Sulu Senior High School.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the result and discussion of the study, the presentation of data followed the sequence according to the order of the research questions indicated in the statement of the problem or research questions.

Social Media Exposure and the Performance of the Students in Mathematics

Table 4.1.1, 4.1.2 and 4.1.3 show the comparisons of the performance of the students in mathematics. The student's first quarter final in General Mathematics grade was utilized as the indicator of their overall performance in mathematics. The students were also divided into three groups according to the number of hours they spent on social media, and each was compared to one another successively using the t-test for two independent samples.

Table 4.1.1
Comparisons of Light Users and Average Users in terms of First Quarter Final Grade in General Mathematics

Group	N	Mean	SD	t-value
Light Users	17	89.47	3.57	1.40
Average Users	57	90.84	3.42	

$\alpha = 0.05$ $df = 72$ $t\text{-crit} = 2.00$

Table 4.1.1 shows the comparison of the performance in mathematics of light users and average users of social media among students. The student's first quarter grade in general mathematics was used as the subject of comparability. The t-test showed a computed t-value of 1.40 at 72 degree of freedom, which is lesser than the t-critical value 2.00 at alpha 0.05 level of significance. This suggests that there is no significant difference in the performance in mathematics of light users and average users of social media.

Table 4.1.2
Comparisons of Light Users and Heavy Users in terms of First Quarter Final Grade in General Mathematics

Group	N	Mean	SD	t-value
Light Users	17	89.47	3.57	0.37
Heavy Users	6	90.50	3.39	

$\alpha = 0.05$ $df = 21$ $t\text{-crit} = 2.08$

Table 4.1.2 shows the comparison of light users and heavy users of social media among students in terms of their performance in mathematics. The student's first quarter grade in general mathematics was used as the subject of comparability. The t-test showed a

computed t-value of 0.37 at $df = 21$. Considering a level of significance at alpha 0.05, the computed t-value is much lesser than the t-critical value of 2.08. This means that the performance of light users and heavy users of social media in mathematics is closely comparable, hence not significantly different.

Table 4.1.3
Comparisons of Average Users and Heavy Users in terms of First Quarter Final Grade in General Mathematics

Group	N	Mean	SD	t-value
Average User	57	90.84	3.42	0.14
Heavy User	6	90.50	3.39	

$\alpha = 0.05$ $df = 61$ $t\text{-crit} = 2.00$

Table 4.1.3 shows the comparison of the performance in mathematics of average users and heavy users of social media among students. The student's first quarter grade in general mathematics was used as the subject of comparability. The t-test showed a t-value of 0.14 at $df = 61$, which is lesser than the t-critical value of 2.00 at 0.05 alpha level of significance. This means that the performance of both groups in mathematics are not significantly different. The t-test showed three different numbers of t-value but hardly the same result on the comparison of the three groups. The t-test showed that the performance in mathematics of light users and average users of social media did not differ significantly, the same goes between the light users and heavy users, and between the average users and heavy users of social media. Based on this outcome, it can be said that the student's performance did not differ significantly regardless of the number of hours they spent on social media. Likewise, it can be said that social media exposure did not have any significant effect on the performance in mathematics of grade 11 GAS 1 and GAS 4 students. Furthermore, this study yielded the same results as the study of Ahmed and Qazi (2011) and Martin (2009) that social media exposure has no significant effect on the performance of the student. Hence, the following null hypotheses are accepted.

1. There is no significant difference in the performance of the students using social media.
2. There is no significant relationship on the performance of students according to the number of hours of using social media.

Comparison of the Social Media Exposure of Male and Female Students and Their Performance in Mathematics

Table 4.2.1
Comparison of Number of Hours Spent on Social Media According to Gender

Group	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Decision
Male	40	1.80	0.56	1.08	H ₀ is accepted
Female	40	1.925	0.47		

$\alpha = 0.05$

df = 78

t-crit = 2.00

Table 4.2.1 shows the comparison of the number of hours spent by the students when grouped according to gender. The researchers used the answers of the students on the checklist-questionnaire to compare the number of hours spent by male students and female students on social media. The table shows that both male and female students have a mean greater than 1 but lesser than 2, this means that both male and female students spent more than an hour but less than 2-3 hours on social media daily.

The table also shows that the mean of the number of hours spent on social media by female students is higher than the mean of the male students, but when compared using t-test, the t-test showed a t-value of 1.08084 at df = 78, which is lesser than the t-critical value of 2.00 at 0.05 alpha level of significance. This means that although female students spend more hours than male students on using social media, the difference is not significantly different.

Table 4.2.2
Comparison of the Performance of Students in General Mathematics when grouped according to gender

Group	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Decision
Female	40	90.78	3.52	1.17	H ₀ is accepted
Male	40	89.83	3.75		

$\alpha = 0.05$

df = 78

t-crit = 2.00

Table 4.2.2 shows the comparison of the performance of students in General Mathematics when grouped according to gender. The t-test showed a computed t-value 1.17 at 78 degree of freedom, which is lesser than the t-critical value of 2.00 considering an 0.05 alpha level of significance. The results showed that there is no significant difference between the performance of students in general mathematics even if they are grouped according to their gender on an alpha 0.05 level of significance. This means that gender is not a deciding factor of the proficiency of students in mathematics. This also mean that the performance in mathematics of male and female students did not differ significantly.

Conclusions

In the light of the findings derived from the study, the following conclusions are presented; Social media exposure did not significantly affect the performance of students in mathematics, the performance in mathematics of light users, average users, and heavy users of social media did not significantly differ from one another, there is no significant difference between the number of hours spent by male and female students, the performance in mathematics of male and female students did not significantly differ.

Recommendations

In light of the findings of the study and based on the presented conclusions, the following are highly recommended:

1. Since social media exposure do not have a significant effect on the performance of the students, school administrators are encouraged to consider integrating social media to teaching mathematics.
2. Schools are also advised to conduct a seminar about the benefits of social media to the studies of the students or any similar topic. This way, both the teachers and the students will be equipped with the knowledge on how to leverage the said platform in the studies of the students.
3. Although this study showed that social media has no significant effect on the performance of the students, Parents are still advised to continually observe their children's daily use of this platform since it is home to many malicious websites and activities.
4. Students should be mindful of the harm of social media and rather utilize it in a beneficial way like watching mathematics tutorials, improving English vocabularies etc.
5. Since this study is inconclusive, future researchers that will conduct a similar study should use larger samples and include different subject areas other than math.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers hereby declare that an informed consent was obtained and followed the ethical process such, as to the researcher handed out a request letter to the senior high coordinator to formally ask for the permission to conduct the study. Upon approval, the researcher retrieved the request letter and proceeded to the distribution of questionnaires.

In administering the questionnaire, the researcher coordinated the adviser of GAS 1 and GAS 4 for the distribution of questionnaires to the eighty students that were selected as respondents. The students were given ten minutes to answer and submit the questionnaire.

The researchers also asked the advisers of both sections about the grades of the students in the first quarter final grades in General Mathematics. After gathering the data, the researcher proceeded to tallying the data scores in order to be fully studied and analyzed.

In addition, the researchers assure that the information gathered from respondents are kept confidential. Plagiarism was strictly observed throughout the research process, and that there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research purposes.

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